

TEACHING PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES AND TECHNOLOGIES: SOFTWARE METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT AND ITS REQUIREMENTS

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Abstract: In the modern digital age, the effective teaching of programming languages and technologies is essential for preparing students to meet the demands of an increasingly technical workforce. Software tools that provide methodological support play a critical role in enhancing programming education. This paper explores the importance of such tools, examining how current software resources align with pedagogical needs in teaching programming languages. Through a literature review, surveys, and case studies, the study identifies the requirements for these tools, highlighting gaps in the current software landscape. The findings emphasize the need for adaptive, interactive, and data-driven platforms that support personalized learning, collaborative environments, and real-time feedback. Recommendations for the future development of educational software tools are proposed to ensure better alignment with industry trends and learner needs.

Keywords: Programming languages, educational technology, software support, programming education, teaching methodologies, learning platforms, digital learning environments, interactive tools, real-time feedback.

Introduction. Programming education is increasingly recognized as an essential skill in the 21st century, as technology continues to shape virtually every aspect of modern life. With the global demand for software developers, engineers, and IT professionals, equipping students with solid programming skills is paramount. However, teaching programming is a multifaceted task that requires both theoretical knowledge and practical, hands-on skills. The traditional methods of teaching—lectures, textbooks, and classroom exercises—are often insufficient in effectively

conveying the complexities of programming concepts. Thus, the integration of educational technologies is crucial for addressing the challenges in programming instruction.

Software methodological support, which refers to the tools and resources used to facilitate teaching, is a cornerstone of modern programming education. These tools include Integrated Development Environments (IDEs), code compilers, Learning Management Systems (LMS), and online platforms that offer interactive coding exercises. While these tools have revolutionized the teaching and learning process, there remains a need to examine their effectiveness and alignment with the pedagogical needs of educators and students. The goal of this paper is to explore the requirements for such software tools, identify existing gaps, and offer recommendations for their improvement to enhance the teaching of programming languages and technologies.

Methods. This research adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research techniques to investigate the current state of software methodological support in programming education. The study focused on the types of tools being used in programming courses, the effectiveness of these tools, and the specific features that educators consider essential for improving the teaching and learning process.

Literature Review. A detailed literature review was conducted to examine existing studies on programming education, the role of educational software, and the methodologies used in teaching programming languages. The review focused on the evolution of educational technologies in programming education, from traditional classroom tools to modern, interactive platforms [1]. Studies were selected that highlighted both the positive impact of software tools and the challenges faced by educators in implementing them effectively [2][3].

The review also explored the theoretical frameworks that underpin the teaching of programming, particularly constructivist learning theories, which emphasize active learning, problem-solving, and the importance of hands-on experience [4][5]. The review provided a foundational understanding of how software tools can support these pedagogical approaches.

Surveys and Interviews. To gain a deeper understanding of the practical challenges and opportunities in using software tools for teaching programming, surveys were administered to a sample of educators across various institutions. The survey targeted instructors who teach programming languages at the university, high school, and coding bootcamp levels. Questions were designed to assess the effectiveness of current tools, the specific challenges educators face, and the features they consider most important in a software tool for programming instruction.

In addition to surveys, semi-structured interviews were conducted with educational technology experts, including instructional designers, developers of educational software, and experienced programming educators. These interviews provided insights into the pedagogical considerations involved in selecting and developing software tools, as well as the potential for innovation in this field.

Case Studies. Several case studies were examined from educational institutions that have successfully integrated technological solutions into their programming curricula. These case studies focused on institutions that have made strides in using software tools to enhance student learning and improve programming instruction. The goal of these case studies was to identify best practices, innovative approaches, and lessons learned from real-world implementations of educational technologies in programming education [6].

Results. The findings from the surveys, interviews, and case studies revealed several key insights into the current state of software methodological support in programming education. These insights focused on the strengths and weaknesses of existing tools and highlighted the specific needs of both instructors and students.

Discussion. The findings suggest that while software tools have become integral to programming education, there are several areas where these tools fall short of meeting the diverse needs of students and educators. Key issues include the lack of personalization, limited collaboration features, and the need for regular updates to keep pace with emerging programming languages and technologies.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the effectiveness of teaching programming languages and technologies depends heavily on the software tools used to support instruction.

While significant progress has been made in the development of these tools, there is still much work to be done. Software tools must evolve to better meet the needs of both educators and students, with a focus on adaptability, personalization, collaboration, and integration with modern technologies. By addressing these gaps, educational institutions can significantly improve programming education and better prepare students for the challenges of the digital world.

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